

Complications and Associated Factors in Gynecological Laparoscopy

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Abstract:

Background: Gynecological laparoscopy is widely recognized for its advantages over traditional open surgery, including reduced postoperative pain, shorter recovery time, and improved cosmetic outcomes. However, despite these benefits, complications such as hemorrhage, organ injury, and postoperative infections can occur, affecting patient safety and outcomes. Identifying the factors that contribute to these complications is crucial for improving surgical success and patient care.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the incidence and types of complications associated with gynecological laparoscopy and to identify patient and procedural factors that influence these outcomes.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted involving 45 female patients who underwent gynecological laparoscopy between January 2020 and December 2020. Data on patient demographics, comorbidities, indications for surgery, and complications were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, employing Chi-square tests, t-tests, and multivariate logistic regression to identify factors associated with complications.

Results: Complications were observed in 20% of the participants, with intraoperative hemorrhage, postoperative infection, and organ injuries being the most common. Higher BMI, hypertension, and longer duration of surgery were significantly associated with increased complications ($p < 0.05$). Multivariate analysis confirmed that high BMI, hypertension, and extended surgical time were independent predictors of complications.

Conclusion: Gynecological laparoscopy is generally safe, but certain patient-related factors, such as high BMI and hypertension, significantly increase the risk of complications. Proper preoperative assessment, risk factor modification, and surgical management are essential to minimize adverse outcomes.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should focus on preoperative optimization, including weight management and control of comorbid conditions, to reduce complication risks. Further research is recommended to develop risk stratification tools and refine surgical protocols, enhancing patient safety and outcomes in gynecological laparoscopy.

Keywords: Gynecological Laparoscopy, Complications, BMI, Hypertension, Surgical Outcomes.

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Introduction

Surgical laparoscopy, which provides a minimally invasive method for diagnosing and treating a variety of gynaecological disorders, has emerged as a fundamental component of contemporary surgical treatment. Because of its related advantages, such as less discomfort after surgery, shorter hospital stays, quicker healing, and fewer scars, this procedure is chosen over standard open surgeries, improving patient outcomes and satisfaction overall [1]. Laparoscopy does have benefits; however there are also hazards involved. Safe patient outcomes might be jeopardised by complications like thromboembolic events, organ damage, postoperative infections, and intraoperative bleeding [2]. Surgeons must deal with these and other serious issues. Patient characteristics, the

experience of the surgeon, and the intricacy of the treatment are some of the factors that influence the likelihood of these complications [3].

An important area of worry in recent years has been the frequency of problems following gynaecological laparoscopy. Research has shown that various patient-related factors can raise the likelihood of unfavourable outcomes, including obesity and concomitant diseases including diabetes and hypertension [4]. As an illustration, obesity is a crucial consideration during preoperative evaluations since it not only complicates the surgical field but also raises the risk of anesthesia-related problems and wound infections [5]. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that the existence of comorbidities such

hypertension increases the risk of surgery since these illnesses might make intraoperative care more challenging and increase recovery times [6]. It is crucial to identify individuals who are more likely to experience complications from gynaecological laparoscopy because obesity and chronic disorders are becoming more and more common worldwide [7]. Healthcare professionals need to create risk classification tools and apply customised perioperative management methods in order to reduce the hazards associated with the changing demographics of patients undergoing these procedures [8]. Not only that, but new factors influencing complication rates have been introduced by recent advances in surgical procedures, like robotic-assisted laparoscopy [9], therefore research and assessment are essential. This study aims to evaluate the incidence and types of complications associated with gynecological laparoscopy and to identify patient and procedural factors that influence these outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a prospective observational study aimed at evaluating the complications associated with gynecological laparoscopy and identifying factors that influence these outcomes.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at Paras HMRI Hospital, Patna, a renowned tertiary care center with a specialized department for gynecological surgery. The study was conducted over a 12-month period from January 2020 to December 2020.

Participants: A total of 45 female patients who underwent gynecological laparoscopy at Paras HMRI Hospital during the study period were included.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Female patients aged 18 years and older.
- Patients undergoing gynecological laparoscopy for either diagnostic or therapeutic purposes.
- Patients who provided informed consent for participation in the study.
- Patients with complete medical and follow-up records.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients undergoing laparoscopy for non-gynecological conditions.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or lost follow-up data.
- Patients with severe systemic illnesses unrelated to gynecological conditions that could affect surgical outcomes.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by including all eligible patients who met the criteria during the study period. Information bias was addressed through standardized data extraction protocols performed by independent researchers.

Data Collection: Data was systematically collected from patient records, including demographics, medical history, indications for surgery, intraoperative findings, details of the surgical procedure, and postoperative complications. The data collection process adhered to confidentiality standards and hospital ethical guidelines.

Procedure: All procedures were conducted in the operating theaters of Paras HMRI Hospital under standardized conditions. Experienced gynecologists performed the surgeries using laparoscopic techniques according to hospital protocols. Complications were documented intraoperatively and during the postoperative period, including minor and major complications.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used for data analysis. The data were summarised using descriptive statistics including means, frequencies, and standard deviations. For categorical data, chi-square tests were used, and t-tests were used for continuous variable analysis. The development of complications was linked to several parameters, which were found using multivariate logistic regression. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

The study included 45 female patients who underwent gynecological laparoscopy between January 2020 and December 2020 at Paras HMRI Hospital, Patna. The mean age of the participants was 32.6 years (SD $\pm$ 6.4), with an age range of 22 to 45 years.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	n (%)
Age Group (years)	
22-30	18 (40%)
31-40	20 (44.4%)
41-45	7 (15.6%)
BMI (kg/m²)	
<18.5 (Underweight)	3 (6.7%)
18.5-24.9 (Normal weight)	25 (55.6%)

25-29.9 (Overweight)	12 (26.7%)
≥30 (Obese)	5 (11.1%)
Comorbidities	
Hypertension	8 (17.8%)
Diabetes Mellitus	5 (11.1%)
None	32 (71.1%)
Indication for Laparoscopy	
Ovarian Cystectomy	20 (44.4%)
Endometriosis	10 (22.2%)
Diagnostic Laparoscopy	7 (15.6%)
Myomectomy	8 (17.8%)

Out of the 45 participants, 9 (20%) experienced complications during or after the laparoscopic procedures.

Table 2: Complications Observed During and After Laparoscopy

Complication	n (%)
Intraoperative Hemorrhage	3 (6.7%)
Bowel Injury	1 (2.2%)
Bladder Injury	1 (2.2%)
Postoperative Infection	2 (4.4%)
Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT)	1 (2.2%)
Port-site Hernia	1 (2.2%)

The relationship between patient characteristics and the occurrence of complications was analyzed using Chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables.

Table 3: Factors Associated with Complications

Factor	Complications (n=9)	No Complications (n=36)	p-value
Age (mean ± SD)	35.1 ± 5.9	31.9 ± 6.3	0.213
BMI (mean ± SD)	26.8 ± 4.5	23.4 ± 3.8	0.042*
Hypertension (n, %)	4 (44.4%)	4 (11.1%)	0.037*
Diabetes Mellitus (n, %)	2 (22.2%)	3 (8.3%)	0.238
Duration of Surgery (minutes)	95.2 ± 18.4	72.5 ± 15.7	0.004**

From the statistical analysis, higher BMI ($p = 0.042$), the presence of hypertension ($p = 0.037$), and longer duration of surgery ($p = 0.004$) were significantly associated with an increased risk of complications. Age and the presence of diabetes

mellitus were not significantly correlated with complications.

A multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to further investigate the independent predictors of complications.

Table 4: Multivariate Analysis of Factors Associated with Complications

Factor	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.12	1.02 - 1.23	0.021*
Hypertension	3.65	1.08 - 12.38	0.037*
Duration of Surgery (minutes)	1.09	1.03 - 1.15	0.002**

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

The multivariate analysis confirmed that higher BMI (OR 1.12, $p = 0.021$), hypertension (OR 3.65, $p = 0.037$), and longer duration of surgery (OR 1.09, $p = 0.002$) were independent predictors of complications in gynecological laparoscopy.

Findings

- A total of 20% of the participants experienced complications related to gynecological laparoscopy.
- The most common complications included intraoperative hemorrhage and postoperative infection.

- Higher BMI, the presence of hypertension, and longer surgery duration were significantly associated with an increased risk of complications.
- The findings highlight the importance of careful preoperative assessment and intraoperative management to minimize the risk of complications, particularly in patients with high BMI and hypertension.

Discussion

The findings revealed that 20% of the participants experienced complications during or after the procedure, highlighting the clinical significance of understanding risk factors associated with these

outcomes. The most common complications observed were intraoperative hemorrhage, postoperative infection, and organ injuries, such as bowel and bladder injuries. This complication rate emphasizes the importance of vigilant surgical management and postoperative care in minimizing adverse outcomes. Analysis of the data identified key factors associated with an increased risk of complications. Higher BMI, hypertension, and longer surgery duration were significantly linked to a higher incidence of complications. Specifically, patients with a higher BMI and those with hypertension had a notably greater likelihood of experiencing complications, suggesting that these conditions may increase the surgical complexity and recovery challenges. Additionally, longer surgical times were associated with more complications, potentially due to increased exposure and operative stress on the patient. Multivariate analysis confirmed that these factors independently contributed to the risk of complications. Higher BMI emerged as a significant predictor, indicating that overweight or obese patients may face greater perioperative challenges. Hypertension, another independent risk factor, underscores the need for careful monitoring and management of blood pressure before, during, and after surgery to mitigate risks. The duration of the surgery also played a critical role, as prolonged procedures can increase the likelihood of intraoperative difficulties and postoperative complications.

In their analysis of difficulties in robotically assisted gynaecological surgeries and laparoscopic procedures, Watrowski et al. (2021) noted that most complications occur during laparoscopic entry, with common problems including ureter and intestine injuries. Surgical phases, damaged organs, and instruments were taken into consideration while identifying risk variables. According to the study underscored the significance of identifying these issues during surgery, since many adverse events are not detected until after the procedure [10].

A study by Belinga et al. (2019) at the Gonesse General Hospital revealed that complications occurred in 6.77% of laparoscopic surgeries, with hemorrhagic episodes being the most frequent. According to this study major procedures were strongly related with complications, with laparotomies being frequently needed as the primary intervention [11]. Le and colleagues (2023) have found a number of risk factors for problems following gynaecologic laparoscopic surgery, such as advanced age, history of abdominal surgery, obesity, and more difficult surgery. According to the study, 0.51% of patients experienced significant difficulties, and 4.64% of cases had minor complications [12].

Conclusion

This study found that gynecological laparoscopy, though generally safe, has a 20% complication rate, particularly among patients with higher BMI, hypertension, and prolonged surgery durations. These risk factors highlight the need for careful preoperative assessment, modification of risk factors, and meticulous surgical management to improve outcomes. Targeted interventions such as weight management, better control of comorbidities, and reducing surgical time can significantly minimize complications. These findings emphasize the importance of personalized care and the need for strategies to enhance patient safety in gynecological laparoscopy.

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